

1 Composition and Evolution of the Solid-Electrolyte Interphase in 2 $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ Electrodes for Na-Ion Batteries: XPS and Auger 3 Parameter Analysis

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12 13 ABSTRACT

14
15 $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ is considered a promising negative electrode for Na-ion batteries; however,
16 poor capacity retention has been reported and the stability of the solid-electrolyte
17 interphase (SEI) could be one of the main actors of this underperformance. The
18 composition and evolution of the SEI in $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrodes is hereby studied by means
19 of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). To overcome typical XPS limitations in the
20 photoelectron energy assignments, the analysis of the Auger parameter is here
21 proposed for the first time in battery materials characterization. We have found that the
22 electrode/electrolyte interface formed upon discharge, mostly composed by carbonates
23 and semicarbonates (Na_2CO_3 , NaCO_3R), fluorides (NaF), chlorides (NaCl) and
24 poly(ethylene oxide)s, is unstable upon electrochemical cycling. Additionally, solid state
25 nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) studies prove the reaction of the polyvinylidene
26 difluoride (PVdF) binder with sodium. The powerful approach used in this work, namely
27 Auger parameter study, enables us to correctly determine the composition of the
28 electrode surface layer without any interference from surface charging or absolute
29 binding energy calibration effects. As a result, the suitability for Na-ion batteries of
30 binders and electrolytes widely used for Li-ion batteries is questioned here.

31
32 KEYWORDS: XPS, Auger parameter, solid-electrolyte interphase, Na-ion battery,
33 $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$

34 35 1. INTRODUCTION

36 Ever since the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) model was described in 1979,¹ many
37 investigations have been focused on the study of the morphology, composition,
38 properties and electrochemical behavior of the SEI in Li-ion batteries.² An anode with an
39 electrochemical potential (μA) above the electrolyte lowest unoccupied molecular
40 orbital (LUMO) will reduce the electrolyte. Therefore, unless the μA is matched to the
41 electrolyte LUMO, a stable passivating SEI layer is needed that prevents electron
42 transfer and continuous electrolyte degradation, while it allows a fast ionic conductance
43 from the anode to the electrolyte.³ Typically, SEI formation leads to a reduction of the
44 battery capacity affecting its lifetime; although, at the same time, its passivating
45 properties are crucial for the electrode stability and, ultimately, for the correct battery
46 operation.⁴

47

48 Na-ion batteries (NIB) are becoming more and more interesting due to their great
49 potential for low cost stationary applications.^{5,6} In fact, as reported in a very recent
50 review,⁷ several studies have been published regarding the composition of the SEI in
51 NIB anodes such as hard-carbons,^{8,9} Sn,¹⁰ Cu₂Sb¹¹ and SnSb-porous carbon nanofiber
52 electrodes.¹² In 2011, Na₂Ti₃O₇, was reported to reversibly react with Na ions at a very
53 low voltage¹³ and was followed by more studies on this^{14,15} and other titanates.¹⁶
54 However, despite the efforts on finding a good combination of electrolyte and binder
55 for Na₂Ti₃O₇, electrode capacity fading is unavoidably obtained in all cases. The
56 formation of a thin SEI in Na₂Ti₃O₇ was recently reported by a combined transmission
57 electron microscopy (TEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) study.¹⁷

58

59 We report herein a thorough study on the composition and evolution of the SEI layer
60 formed on Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes upon electrochemical cycling. X-ray photoelectron
61 spectroscopy (XPS) measurements at different states of charge on electrodes never
62 exposed to air have revealed the SEI composition as well as its instability upon cycling.
63 Complementary solid state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) studies have proved the
64 degradation of the PVdF binder.

65

66 2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

67 2.1. Electrode Preparation.

68 The electroactive material, Na₂Ti₃O₇, was synthesized in-house via a ceramic route from
69 precursors: anatase titanium oxide (99.9%, Alfa Aesar) and sodium carbonate
70 monohydrate (>99.5%, Aldrich) as reported previously by Senguttuvan and co-
71 workers.¹³ Structural characterization of the sodium titanate was accomplished by
72 means of X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Bruker D8 diffractometer with a Cu K α source.
73 According to the XRD pattern shown in Figure S1 of the Supporting Information, the
74 diffraction peaks of the synthesized material match very well with those of Na₂Ti₃O₇,
75 space group *P2₁/m*. The phase purity is evidenced by the good fit and the refined cell
76 parameters are in close agreement with those reported in the literature,¹³ c.f. Table S1
77 of the Supporting Information. Electrodes were prepared by mixing the synthesized
78 sodium titanate with carbon (C65) and polyvinylidene difluoride (PVdF, Solef 5130) in
79 the weight ratio 88:10:2. Electrodes were coated on Al foil and dried at 80 °C in a vacuum
80 oven for 24 h, pressed at 5 ton and vacuum-dried for 2 h at 80 °C.

81

82 2.2. Electrochemical Measurements.

83 Swagelok cells were assembled in an Ar-filled glovebox using metallic sodium as negative
84 and reference electrode and glass fiber disk separators. 1 M NaClO₄ (Fischer Scientific)
85 in a mixture (1:1) of ethylene carbonate and propylene carbonate (EC, PC, Acros
86 Organics) was used as the electrolyte, which is the most studied configuration.¹³⁻¹⁵
87 Electrochemical tests of the assembled cells were performed at 25 °C using VMP3
88 potentiostat (Bio-Logic SAS) at C/10 in the 0.05 to 1.6 V range. The charge/discharge
89 profiles are shown in Figure 1a.

90
 91 Figure 1. (a) Electrochemical potential profile of $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$ electrodes during the first
 92 three cycles, points where XPS analysis is performed are pointed with arrows. (b) C 1s
 93 XPS core level spectra for electrodes before cycling and at points of the charge/discharge
 94 curve indicated in
 95 panel a.

96
 97 2.3. X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS).

98 Electrode surface was investigated at different charge states using a Phoibos 150 XPS
 99 spectrometer and a nonmonochromatic Mg $K\alpha$ source ($h\nu = 1253.6$ eV). Electrodes were
 100 inserted into the XPS vacuum chamber using an Ar-filled transfer system. Cycled
 101 electrodes were rinsed with PC prior to XPS experiments. High resolution scans were
 102 acquired at 100 W, 20 eV pass energy and 0.1 eV energy step. Depth profiling was done
 103 using a focused ion gun for 1 keV Ar^+ with a sputtering rate of 0.2 $\text{\AA}/\text{s}$, which was
 104 determined from measurements in a Ta_2O_5 standard calibrated with laser profilometry
 105 and corrected by the relative sputtering cross section of our particular compound. X-ray
 106 beam and ion beam power and energy were tested in reference samples to minimize
 107 the sample damage. For the five samples where the graphitic carbon peak is visible,
 108 calibration of the binding energy scale was set using the reference at 284.4 eV, for the
 109 other three samples, the same shift measured for the previous five was used; it is well-
 110 known that in Li-ion batteries this would not be possible because the Li ions insert into
 111 the graphite structure to form Li_xC_6 that results in a lower binding energy of the C-C
 112 bond; however, as reported up to date, Na ions do not insert into graphite and they do
 113 so into hard carbon only.^{8,18} Therefore, selecting the graphite peak as the reference for
 114 the binding energy reference is the best option. However, due to differential surface
 115 charging effects, the aforementioned calibration procedure is not sufficient for a full
 116 determination of the surface layer composition. As it will be discussed later, the
 117 evaluation of the Auger parameter will provide crucial information on this regard, for

118 this, the Na KL₂₃L₂₃ peaks were also measured and along with the photoelectron Na 1s
119 peak were fitted using the CasaXPS software. Voigt functions (70% Gaussian and 30%
120 Lorentzian) were used in the fits to determine the peak positions, the fitting parameters
121 were obtained using a Levenberg–Marquardt optimization algorithm starting from
122 different initial guess parameters that always led to the same result.

123 124 2.3. Solid State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR).

125 Solid state NMR experiments were performed to check the binder degradation;
126 electrodes were scratched out of the aluminum current collector and the powders of
127 the soaked and discharged electrodes were fitted into the rotors inside an Ar-filled
128 glovebox. ¹⁹F solid state NMR data were collected on a Bruker 500 MHz spectrometer,
129 at an operating frequency of 470 MHz, with a 1.3 mm probe. Rotors were spun at a
130 magic-angle-spinning (MAS) rate of 50 kHz. A rotor synchronized Hahn echo (90°-τ-180°-
131 τ-acq.) sequence was used with a 90° pulse of 3.6 μs and a delay of 40 s. Spectra are
132 referenced to secondary LiF (-201 ppm).¹⁹ Approximately 100 000 scans were collected
133 per ¹⁹F solid-state NMR spectrum.

134 135 3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

136 The SEI formation and evolution was followed by XPS from the Cl 2p, C 1s, O 1s, F 1s, Na
137 1s photoelectron peaks and Na KL₂₃L₂₃ Auger peaks. Among these, the most important
138 photoemission line was the C 1s peak (Figure 1b) recorded at different voltage values
139 during discharge/charge, as shown in the profiles of Figure 1a. The assignments of the C
140 1s components have been done on the basis of previous XPS studies of carbon-based
141 materials.²⁰ Because there are different possibilities for C–O bonds on the surface of
142 graphitic materials, the peak energies will be assigned following the trends reported by
143 Xie and Sherwood.²¹ However, absolute binding energies for cycled electrodes are
144 slightly different to the ones reported in the literature for reference materials, the
145 reason being the non-uniform charging effects of non conducting microdomains of salt
146 residuals and reduction products on the surface. XPS data of reference compounds such
147 as PVdF, C65 carbon, NaClO₄ and Na₂CO₃, along with their internal energy shifts, were
148 collected to corroborate the peak assignment. Finally, the majority of peaks could be
149 assigned from relative peak positions obtained from binding energy differences²² and
150 after calculation of the corresponding Auger parameter²³ which, involving
151 measurements of both Auger and photoelectron line energies, provides abundant
152 chemical state information without the necessity or concern for charge correction and
153 work function measurements. In Table S2 of the Supporting Information, experimental
154 data of photoemission lines and Auger parameters from reference samples measured in
155 our XPS are available.

156
157 One of the key features in the C 1s photoelectron spectra of the pristine and OCV
158 electrodes is the component at 284.4 eV assigned to graphitic-like compounds with a
159 marked asymmetry toward high binding energies due to the presence of C–C and C–H
160 bonds from hydrocarbon contamination and from the excitation of electron–hole
161 pairs,²⁴ the asymmetry in the latter case will depend on the density of states at the Fermi
162 level and it could mask the real contribution from hydrocarbon contamination, which
163 most probably is overestimated. In the 290.5–290.8 eV range, contributions from
164 organic carbonate contamination and a shake-up feature corresponding to a Π–Π*

165 transition from graphitic-like compounds will appear.²⁵ The graphitic-like component in
166 the XPS spectra of the pristine and OCV electrodes mainly corresponds to the conductive
167 additive. The presence of polyvinylidene difluoride (PVdF, $-(CF_2-CH_2)_n-$) in the pristine
168 and OCV samples is revealed by two equal peaks, one at 286.4 eV from the $-CH_2$ and
169 another one at 290.9 eV from the fluorinated carbon, overlapped with the $\pi-\pi^*$
170 transition.²⁶ As the sodiation process evolves, the graphitic-like signal decreases. Indeed,
171 the peak at 284.4 eV progressively disappears upon discharge between 0.6 and 0.2 V
172 until its complete extinction at 0.18 V, showing the formation of a SEI layer that
173 completely covers the electrode surface. Based on the empirical relationship between
174 the escape length of a photoelectron and its kinetic energy, these results are consistent
175 with a minimum SEI layer thickness of 5 nm for photoelectrons with a kinetic energy
176 around 1000 eV.^{27,28} Upon charge, a small shoulder appears at 284.4 eV from the
177 underlying graphitic carbon indicating a thinning or cracking of the SEI layer. After a
178 second discharge, the shoulder disappears as the SEI layer regenerates fully covering the
179 electrode surface again. This process of SEI formation upon discharge and partial
180 dissolution upon charge is repeated along several cycles, shortly after, the capacity fade
181 is too large and the cell stops working (not shown).

182
183 As the graphitic-like component disappears during discharge, other components
184 become more prominent: carbon atoms surrounded by one oxygen atom such as
185 sodium alkoxides (NaOR) and poly(ethylene oxide) $(-CH_2-CH_2-O-)_n$ oligomers (PEO) at
186 286.1–286.5 eV;^{12,22} and carbons in a three-oxygen environment like sodium alkyl
187 carbonates (NaCO₃R, R = different long-chain alkyl groups)²⁹ and sodium carbonate
188 (Na₂CO₃) with contributions at 291–291.5 eV²² instead of 289.4 eV¹¹ due to differential
189 charging effects. The presence of NaCO₃R involves an additional feature at 287.5–288
190 eV originated by the first carbon atom in the alkane chain.^{12,22} Finally, concerning the
191 evolution of the C 1s PVdF components during cycling, it has been previously reported³⁰
192 that sodium atoms can chemically interact with PVdF strongly influencing the fluorine
193 electronic structure, but perturbing the carbon backbone only slightly by additionally
194 splitting the $-CF_2$ and $-CH_2$ components, as indicated in Figure 1b.

195
196 The study of the XPS F 1s and O 1s peaks allow us a better understanding of the surface
197 layer composition (Figure 2).

198

Figure 2. XPS F 1s and O 1s spectra are shown for pristine electrodes and at different charge states

In the F 1s photoelectron line, a faint peak corresponding to NaF (685 eV) appears as soon as the electrode and electrolyte are assembled. Typically, this is a consequence of a dehydrofluorination reaction in the PVdF binder that results in NaF formation, as it has been previously reported for Li-ion batteries.³¹ To fully confirm the NaF formation, we performed ¹⁹F solid state NMR experiments on several electrodes, as shown in Figure 3; in panels b, c and d of this figure, the formation of NaF (-221 ppm)¹⁹ is revealed even in the pristine electrode (Figure 3b), indicating that sodium fluoride is initially formed in the bulk region during electrode preparation because no traces are detected in the surface by XPS. After comparing the relative peak intensities within the same NMR spectra, taking the PVdF intensity as a reference, we can conclude that the intensity of the NaF peak increases upon discharge. Going back to the XPS results, the main peak in the F 1s spectrum corresponds to -CF₂ groups from PVdF (688.15 eV) in the pristine and OCV electrodes.²⁶ However, as observed in the C 1s spectrum, the -CF₂ component in the F 1s spectrum evolves toward higher binding energies upon discharge as a result of surface charging and final state effects, such as screening induced by Na doping that involves changes in the intensity and core level binding energy shift.³⁰ The evolution of the PVdF was further confirmed by our NMR experiments of the discharged electrode compared to a PVdF reference sample (Figure 3a,d). The disappearance of the NMR signals at -78, -88 and -93 ppm, typical from PVdF,³² and the appearance of a very narrow doublet at -68 and -70 ppm in the NMR spectrum of the discharged electrode indicates the presence of residual -CHF and/or -CF₂ bonding resulting from the degradation of PVdF. This lack of stability toward sodium doping could be one of the factors affecting the larger capacity fade of PVdF-based titanate electrodes when compared with other binders such as sodium alginate¹⁷ which are still affected by capacity fading. In the F 1s XPS spectrum (Figure 2), the -CF₂ component of the PVdF disappears after the SEI formation at 0.18 V and partially reappears after every charge step. Although this cyclic behavior is only clear after the first discharge for NaF and

230 considering that signal-to-noise ratio for the fluorine spectrum is rather poor, the global
231 trend of the F 1s spectrum would agree with a partial dissolution of the SEI layer.
232

233
234 Figure 3. ^{19}F MAS NMR spectra of (a) PVdF reference sample, (b) pristine $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$
235 electrode, (c) electrode at OCV and (d) electrode discharged down to 0.05 V vs Na^+/Na .
236 The inset in panel d shows details of the evolution of the PVdF signal into CHF- and CF_2 -
237 based compounds. Spinning side bands of the most intense isotropic signals are labeled as
238 “ss”.

239 As it can be seen in the right panel of Figure 2, the O 1s spectrum from the pristine and
240 OCV electrodes has a dominating component at ~ 531 eV that corresponds to $\text{Na}_2\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_7$;
241 this main component is extended toward higher binding energies (531–531.5 eV) due to
242 the presence of hydroxides. The secondary peak at 532–533 eV can be attributed to
243 some residual amount of carbonates, moisture and, for the OCV sample, also some
244 NaClO_4 residuals. As the electrode starts its discharge, a thick layer covering the
245 electrode surface is quickly formed that is composed of sodium carbonate (~ 532.8 eV)
246 and alkylcarbonate (~ 534 eV and ~ 532.9 eV), along with PEO (~ 533 eV), which
247 consolidates upon discharge.²² The PEO results from direct polymerization of EC where
248 alkylcarbonates could act as catalysts.^{33,34} In the 531.5–532.5 eV range, the sodium
249 alkoxide should also appear, but given the overlapping with other components, it is very
250 difficult to determine its existence.³⁵ Taking into account the measured shift between
251 the O 1s and Cl 2p peaks in a NaClO_4 reference sample, the contribution from traces of
252 NaClO_4 would appear at 533.8 eV in this case. At ~ 535 eV, there is a component that
253 corresponds to an overlayer of chemisorbed oxygen²¹ as a result of the perchlorate
254 anion dissociation.³⁶ The PEO contribution in the O 1s spectrum is attenuated upon
255 charge, in agreement with the observed behavior of the PEO component at 286.5 eV in
256 the C 1s peak, indicating a partial dissolution of this species. However, carbonate,
257 alkoxide, alkylcarbonate and PEO signals are very close to each other and it is very
258 difficult to establish that only PEO is dissolved upon charge. Conventional XPS analysis
259 is not sufficient to obtain a complete picture of the SEI evolution; therefore, the study
260 of the Auger parameter will be crucial to go one step further, enabling us to identify
261 components of the SEI and their stability during electrochemical cycling.
262

263 XPS measurements of the Cl 2p level (Figure 4, bottom panel) show traces of NaClO₄ in
 264 the electrode surface; however, as it will be discussed later, one of the most striking
 265 features is the NaCl formed spontaneously at OCV. The photoinduced decomposition of
 266 sodium perchlorate and sodium chlorate has been previously studied³⁶ and, indeed, part
 267 of the NaCl observed could be a result of a decomposition of the perchlorate induced by
 268 the Mg K α radiation from the XPS source. However, in our study, we carefully screened
 269 different low power X-ray beam conditions to partially avoid this problem. As a result,
 270 the Cl 2p level measured at different charge states reveals the presence of NaCl at OCV,
 271 whereas the dominant component in the electrochemically cycled samples corresponds
 272 to NaClO₄ traces not removed during the electrode washing (Figure S2 of the Supporting
 273 Information). This points out the spontaneous formation of NaCl at the very beginning
 274 of electrode preparation prior to any cycling, which will then be buried by the other SEI
 275 components such as carbonates and alkylcarbonates.
 276

277 Figure 4. XPS spectra (F 1s, O 1s and Cl 2p) at different depths of a discharged electrode:
 278 outermost surface (black) and after removing 1 nm (blue), 5 nm (red) and 10 nm (green)
 279 with Ar⁺ bombardment.

280 As previously mentioned, the full identification of the SEI composition is rather
 281 complicated, the main reasons being the overlapping of several components in the
 282 photoelectron peaks along with partial surface charging and the difficulties to establish
 283 an absolute binding energy calibration. To overcome these limitations, an approach
 284 never used before for the characterization of the SEI layer is herein proposed. This
 285 consists in the analysis of the Auger parameter (α) for Na, which results from
 286 determining the energy shift between the Na 1s photoelectron line and the Na KL₂₃L₂₃
 287 Auger line, which is a doubly ionized final state more sensitive to chemical shifts.

288 Indeed, the analysis of the Auger parameter is hampered in Li based compounds
 289 because the Auger lines are not easily reachable by XPS. However, for Na-based
 290 compounds, it turns out to be a very powerful tool. In Figure 5, the fits used to determine
 291 the positions of the Na 1s and Na KL₂₃L₂₃ peaks are shown. Once the peak positions are
 292 known from the fits, the Auger parameter is calculated; all these results are included in
 293 Table S3 of the Supporting Information.
 294

295
 296 Figure 5. XPS data from Na in Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes at different charge states. On the left
 297 panel is the 1s photoemission line and on the right panel the Auger KL₂₃L₂₃ transition. The
 298 circles correspond to the experimental data and the solid lines are the fits; all curves are
 299 color coded according to their charge state.

300
 301 The outcome of this analysis is shown in Figure 6, and the measured values with the
 302 corresponding compound assignment can be found in Table 1.

303 Table 1. Experimental Auger Parameters of the Na-based Compounds of the SEI Layer
 304 at Different Charge States along with Their Assignment

charge state	modified Auger parameter (eV) ^a	compound
pristine	206.0	Na ₂ Ti ₃ O ₇ ^b
OCV	2061.8	NaCl
0.81 V	2061.3	Na ₂ CO ₃
0.18 V	2061.1	Na ₂ CO ₃ ⁺ + NaCO ₃ -R ^b
1 st discharge	2061.1	Na ₂ CO ₃ ⁺ + NaCO ₃ -R ^b
1 st charge	2061.3	Na ₂ CO ₃
2 nd discharge	2061.1	Na ₂ CO ₃ ⁺ + NaCO ₃ -R ^b
3 rd charge	2061.2	Na ₂ CO ₃ ⁺ + NaCO ₃ -R ^b

305 ^a $\alpha+h\nu = E_k(KL_{23}L_{23}) + E_b(1s)$. ^b Approximate values extrapolated from ref. 37.

306
 307 Because we are dealing with a high binding energy photo- electron line, namely Na 1s,
 308 the detected photoelectrons will have a very low kinetic energy and a very short inelastic

309 mean free path; therefore, the resulting peak will be integrated over the outermost
310 surface region. This means that surface sensitivity will be enhanced if compared with
311 other elements such as Cl, C, O and F. This anticipates the fact that with the Auger
312 parameter the presence of subsurface NaF cannot be detected, although its presence
313 was previously confirmed by F 1s XPS and ¹⁹F-NMR measurements. In Figure 6, the Auger
314 parameter is plotted for different states of charge of the electrode. The Auger parameter
315 for the pristine and OCV electrodes nicely fits with the presence of Na₂Ti₃O₇ and NaCl,
316 respectively.³⁷ The NaCl formation is thus further confirmed by the analysis of the
317 determined Auger parameter on the OCV sample. Upon discharge, the formation of
318 Na₂CO₃ is quickly evidenced covering any trace of NaCl. Later, at voltages below 0.2 V,
319 the carbonate itself is partially covered by an alkylcarbonate layer that is partially
320 dissolved upon charge as corroborated by Auger parameters that show again the
321 presence of sodium carbonate. This is a cyclic behavior that agrees with the evolution of
322 the O 1s photoelectron peak.

323

324 Once the composition of the surface layer was known, we sought for a better
325 understanding of its structure by performing an XPS depth profiling using a 1 keV Ar ion
326 beam (Figure 4). After the F 1s, O 1s and Cl 2p signals were observed at different depths
327 in a discharged electrode, it was observed that, as expected, the NaF peak intensity
328 increases in the subsurface region, the chemisorbed oxygen and alkylcarbonate
329 overlayer disappears after a few seconds of ion bombardment and, finally, the NaCl
330 concentration increases in the subsurface region while residual NaClO₄ is removed from
331 the surface. From the depth profiling results shown in Figure 4 and the Auger parameter
332 analysis from Figures 5 and 6, it can be clearly determined that chemisorbed oxygen and
333 alkylcarbonate are in the outermost surface region coexisting with PEO partially buried.
334 This overlayer is covering a rough layer of carbonates that has grown on top of the
335 spontaneously formed NaCl and NaF.

336

337 At the same time, it could be initially concluded that the observed signal increase for
338 NaF could also be due to the removal of the residual NaClO₄ overlayer. However, the
339 NMR experiment indicates that a significant concentration of NaF is present, although it
340 cannot be fully detected by XPS due to its location in a buried region of the electrode.
341 Subsequent ion bombardment in the discharged electrode shows that the SEI layer
342 thickness is around 5–10 nm, as initially estimated from the photoelectron escape
343 length. After 5 nm of the surface is removed, the signals of the NaF and NaCl significantly
344 decrease while the component corresponding to the Na₂Ti₃O₇ appears at 531 eV in the
345 O 1s spectrum: a clear sign of SEI removal. At this point, if we keep etching the surface
346 beyond 10 nm, other compounds not detected at the initial stages of discharge could be
347 induced by the ion, so we cannot fully conclude anything about the SEI composition
348 beyond this point. Certainly, ion beam induced surface damage is something that has to
349 be considered for long sputtering processes, i.e., more than 1 nm.

350

351 4. CONCLUSIONS

352 The instability upon charge of the SEI formed in Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes has been observed
353 for the first time. Despite the galvanostatic curves only show a feature of SEI formation
354 at the first discharge (Figure 1a), the SEI is partially dissolved upon every charge. This
355 surface layer is composed of a thin overlayer of chemisorbed oxygen, alkylcarbonates

356 and PEO that covers the solid layer of sodium carbonates, NaF and NaCl (~5 nm), being
357 the NaCl formed spontaneously at the beginning (OCV) by decomposition of the
358 electrolyte salt. The NaF is formed during electrode preparation having its origin in the
359 PVdF dehydrofluorination reactions. In contrast to the SEI in Li-ion batteries, the SEI
360 formed in Na₂Ti₃O₇ electrodes is thinner and has more inorganic components than
361 organic ones, with PEO and alkylcarbonates being partially soluble and originating a
362 continuous SEI reformation. The predominance of inorganic compounds in the SEI
363 agrees with the SEI composition in hard carbon anodes; meanwhile, the thinning or
364 cracking of the SEI has been reported for Sn- and Sb-based anodes. In our case, reactions
365 of the PVdF binder have also been spotted as demonstrated by NMR and XPS
366 experiments, indirectly through formation of NaF as a result of the HF formation by
367 dehydrofluorination of the PVdF and directly through the evolution of the -CF₂ groups.
368 The observed SEI instability involves a continuous electrolyte degradation which along
369 with the binder degradation will certainly contribute to the observed capacity fade and
370 reduced cycle life. Identification of compounds and their evolution has been possible
371 thanks to the analysis of the Auger parameter, applied for the first time to the SEI study,
372 which has provided clear information where conventional XPS analysis was not sufficient
373 for a correct binding energy assignment.

374
375 The current electrode formulation in terms of binder and electrolyte is far from ideal,
376 although the Li counterparts have been proven to work with Li-ion batteries. Several
377 alternatives have been proposed in the literature for this and other electrode materials,
378 namely binders such as sodium alginate-(NaAlg) or sodium carboxymethylcellulose (Na-
379 CMC) and electrolytes such as NaBF₄, NaPF₆ and NaTFSI; still, their performance is not
380 comparable to their Li counterparts. For sodium titanate electrodes, all the efforts have
381 been focused on the use of NaAlg and PVdF along with NaClO₄ or NaFSI,¹⁷ the obtained
382 performance results are pretty similar in all cases and capacity fades dramatically before
383 20 cycles. We consider that the higher reactivity of Na compared with Li and the catalytic
384 activity of titanate materials might be among the factors influencing the
385 underperformance of binders and electrolytes.

386
387 To improve the Na₂Ti₃O₇ performance, the exploration of protective coatings for the
388 electrode active material might result in a decrease of the catalytic activity of the
389 titanate rendering the system more stable.

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